

Electrochemical analysis with nanoparticle based biosystems

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Abstract

A general overview on the application of electrochemical analysis for biosensing purposes in relation to the use of nanoparticles is given. Several examples related to the applications of voltammetric, potentiometric, conductometric, impedimetric and scanning electrochemical microscope based methods in nanoparticle characterization, detection and quantification are described and discussed in terms of sensitivity, selectivity as well as other analytical performance parameters. The advantages of direct (without previous dissolving) vs. indirect (after dissolving or enhancement) detection of nanoparticles using both voltammetric and potentiometric techniques are discussed in relation to bioassay applications. The final part of this review describes the use of scanning electrochemical microscopy to characterize and investigate intrinsic properties of metal and semiconductor nanoparticles. This technique offers a promising approach to future bioanalytical applications, especially with regard to single molecule detection. The reported electrochemical methods show clear advantages for DNA and protein detection in comparison to other techniques, even though the application in real samples as well as the development of final market oriented designs is still in process.

Keywords: Nanoparticles, quantum dots, DNA, protein, electrochemical analysis, voltammetry, potentiometry, conductometry, impedance, scanning electrochemical microscopy.

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1. Introduction

Investigations on nanoparticles (NPs) have increased rapidly in recent years due to their size and shape-dependent physical, chemical and electrochemical properties which make them extremely useful in sensing and biosensing applications.¹ The size and the composition of a NP seems to be advantageous over the corresponding bulk structure because a target binding event (i.e. DNA hybridization or immunoreaction) involving the NPs can have a significant effect on its optical (change of the light absorption / emission) or electrochemical properties (oxidation / reduction current onto a transducing platform) offering novel alternatives for bioanalysis.

The application of NPs in biosensors is strongly related to their properties that depend in certain mode from the synthesis (quality of nanoparticles) and posterior modifications (chemical and biological). The NPs preparation procedure, either in colloidal solutions or grown on solid substrates, have been extensively reviewed.² Along with synthetic advances for varying the size, shape, and composition of nanostructured materials has come the ability to tailor their binding affinities for various biomolecules through surface modification and engineering.

Many types of NPs of different sizes and compositions are now available, which facilitate their electrochemical related application in enzyme based sensors, immunosensors and DNA sensors^{3,4,5}. Nevertheless biological or molecular coating which will act as a bioactive and selective interface is necessary to be attached to the nanoparticles prior their application in biosensing systems. The functionalization of inorganic nanoparticles by means of evolutionary optimized biological components concerns an important point. Since the nanoparticles and biomolecules typically meet at the same nanometer length scale, this interdisciplinary approach will contribute to the establishment of a novel field, descriptively termed biomolecular nanotechnology or nanobiotechnology.⁶

In addition to the chemical and biological modification (including coatings with antibodies, DNA, cells etc.) the NP characterisation and quantification play a crucial role for the final biosensing application. The optical and electrochemical properties of NPs offer various signal transduction modes, including simultaneous approaches (optical and electrochemical) not available with other materials.^{7,8,9}

The range of the used NPs is as large as the range of potential applications in biosensors and depends strongly from the applications, the biomolecules to detect as well as the type of the sample to be analysed. Some examples, according to the applied electrochemical technique, will be revised in this manuscript with the objective to show the large range of the NP detection possibilities offered and discuss novel opportunities for future applications in bioanalysis.

2. Voltammetric techniques

Voltammetric techniques represent certainly the most widely used methods in electrochemical analysis including sensing applications based on metal and semiconductor nanoparticles. This is due to its relatively low cost, enormous diffusion of the related instruments required for such techniques in addition to the enhanced sensitivities achieved in the last decades by means of new electrode materials.

The application of voltammetric techniques for either nanoparticles characterization / analysis or (bio)sensing purposes is based on two detection methodologies: a) direct methods, without any previous chemical dissolution of NPs and b) indirect methods, based on i) previous dissolution of NPs obtaining and analysing the corresponding ions or ii) using catalytic methods via the use of other species.

Despite the exceptional sensitivity achievable by the dissolution of the metal nanoparticles and the following voltammetric determination of the liberated metal ions, these methods require an extra analytical step which often needs the use of toxic/concentrated chemical agents. By contrary the nanoparticle characterization / detection mode based on direct methodologies does not use any preliminary dissolution step or any indirect catalytic technique prior application offering advantages for (bio)sensor applications in terms of the fast response, procedure simplicity and reduced cost of analysis.

In the following section the most reported direct and indirect voltammetric techniques in relation to nanoparticle characterisation, analysis as well as applications in sensors and biosensors are described.

2.1. Direct voltammetric detection

Direct voltammetric detection of nanoparticles consists of a so called solid-state analysis, where the metals forming the nanoparticles are detected electrochemically without any preliminary dissolution step to liberate the metal ions in solution. However, this type of detection needs a direct contact between the electrode surface and the metal itself and excludes from the detection a large portion of non-touching particles. Despite the loss of sensitivity that could result from this phenomenon, in comparison with techniques exploiting the total nanoparticles dissolution and all metal ions detected, direct detections achieve more rapid responses and still considerable limit of detections. Details on the experimental platforms as well as the performances of the biosensing devices developed are revised.

A pioneering work in the field of NP detection in aqueous medium has been carried out by Costa-Garcia et al. in 1995 where a direct stripping solid-state detection of gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) on a carbon paste electrode was performed using both unlabelled and antibody-labelled AuNPs by means of differential pulse anodic stripping voltammetry. Detection limits of 1.78×10^{-8} M and 1.38×10^{-8} M for AuNPs and immunogold (antibody-conjugated AuNPs), respectively, were reached¹⁰.

Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles have been characterized in 2001 by Marken et al. using indium tin oxide based electrodes demonstrating that both the adhesion and the electrochemical reactivity of Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles at the electrode surfaces were strongly affected by the solution composition and pH¹¹.

Important contributions to direct electrochemical characterization/detection of metal and semiconductor nanoparticles have been given by our group with some works regarding the differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) analysis of AuNPs at graphite epoxy composite electrode (GECE)¹² and analysis of CdS quantum dots at Bi(NO₃)₃-modified GECE^{13,14} (Fig. 1).

Following these electroanalytical methodologies aimed to the simple detection of nanoparticles, many sensing applications can be found and exploiting the same principles, most of them regarding affinity assays (DNA and protein analyses).

Solid-state detection of NPs has been applied in numerous immunoassays and DNA analysis exploiting the intrinsic electrochemical properties of the metal NPs used as tracers. Wang's and our group used magnetic particles as platform to perform the immunological interactions or the DNA hybridization events (Fig. 2). After the specific interaction with the secondary NP-labelled probe, these magnetic particles were collected onto the electrode surface by means of a permanent magnet either positioned below the screen-printed electrode surface^{15,16,17}(Fig.2A), or inserted inside the electrode body to detect DNA^{18,19} (Fig. 2B) and protein⁷ (Fig.2C). DPV analyses were performed to quantify the metal NPs collected through the biospecific interaction and that are related to the target analyte concentration (DNA/protein). Very low limits of detection were achieved using this magnetic particle collection, reaching the lowest value of 150 pg/mL DNA segment related to the breast cancer gene¹⁵ and 260 pg/mL to the human IgG protein⁷.

Similar approaches were adopted collecting the streptavidin-coated beads with immobilized biotinylated-DNA probe and the DNA target, by means of a biotin-modified carbon paste electrode. Only after this collection the specific single-stranded DNA binding protein (SSB)-Au labelled was added. The oxidation of AuNPs was followed by square wave voltammetry. This approach allowed the authors to reach a limit of detection of 2.17 pM of target DNA²⁰.

A different platform consists of the immobilization of the target DNA onto the surface of a pencil graphite electrode and then the incubation with a probe Au-labelled DNA strand which specifically interacts with a target DNA section of interest, and able to detect mutations. The direct oxidation of AuNPs onto the pencil graphite electrode was then followed by DPV techniques (Fig. 3). The limit of detection stated by the authors was of 0.81 pM of target DNA²¹.

Very recently an interesting application using AuNPs was demonstrated by Kerman et al. (2007). They were able to detect a protein phosphorylation event which being coupled with the biotinylation of the kinase substrate, allowed the specific interaction with streptavidin-coated AuNPs. A direct DPV analysis of the captured AuNPs onto screen-printed carbon electrodes was then performed. The electrochemical response

obtained from Au nanoparticles enabled monitoring the activity of the kinase and its substrate, as well as the inhibition of small molecule inhibitors on protein phosphorylation²² (Fig. 4)

2.2. Indirect voltammetric detection

2.2.1. Voltammetric stripping analysis

Very sensitive nanoparticle detection can be performed by oxidative dissolution of the nanoparticle into the corresponding metal ions followed by a powerful electroanalytical technique such as stripping voltammetry. Because of its effective “built-in” preconcentration (deposition) step, the technique offers remarkably low (picomolar) detection limits. Different voltammetric techniques, such as normal pulse voltammetry (NPV), differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) and square wave voltammetry (SWV) can be applied in order to obtain the analytical signal. Gold, silver and heavy metal based nanoparticles have been the most reported.

Gold nanoparticles (AuNP). One of the first works with indirect detection of AuNPs by voltammetric stripping analysis was reported by Dequaire et al²³. They developed a sensitive electrochemical immunoassay for immunoglobulin G (IgG) using AuNPs as labels. After an oxidative gold label metal dissolution step in an acidic solution, gold(III) ions were indirectly determined by anodic stripping voltammetry at a single-use carbon-based screen-printed electrode and IgG at concentration levels of $3 \cdot 10^{-12}$ M was possible to be detected. The high performance of the method is related to the sensitive ASV determination of gold(III) at a screen-printed electrode (detection limit of gold (III) around $5 \cdot 10^{-9}$ M) due to the release of a large number of gold(III) ions from each AuNP anchored on the immunocomplex.

Related to DNA analysis using AuNPs as labels, an electrochemical DNA detection method was proposed by Authier et al²⁴. for the sensitive quantification of an amplified 406-base pair human cytomegalovirus DNA sequence (HCMV DNA). The assay relies on the hybridization of the single-stranded target HCMV DNA with an oligonucleotide-

modified-AuNP probe followed by the release of the gold metal atoms anchored on the hybrids by oxidative metal dissolution using a 0.1 M HBr solution containing 1×10^{-4} M of Br_2 . The indirect determination of the solubilized gold (III) ions by anodic stripping voltammetry at a sandwich-type screen-printed microband electrode allowing the detection of 5 pM amplified HCMV DNA fragment is reported.

Silver nanoparticles (AgNPs). AgNPs have been also used for DNA analysis by Cai et al.²⁵. A very sensitive oligonucleotide target detection (0.5 pM) was obtained using anodic stripping voltammetry for the indirect determination of the solubilised Ag(I) ions at a carbon fiber ultramicroelectrode (Fig. 5).

Semiconductor nanocrystals or quantum dots (QD). Other kinds of NPs widely used as labels for both protein and DNA determination are semiconductors nanocrystals such as QDs.

Dai et al.²⁶ reported a nanoparticle-based biosensing assay for sugars, based on their interaction with surface-functionalized lectins. This bioassay involved the competition between a nanocrystal (CdS)-labeled sugar and the target sugar for the carbohydrate binding sites on lectin, previously immobilized in a mixed self-assembly monolayer on a gold surface and the detection of the dissolved cadmium from the captured nanocrystal through highly sensitive electrochemical stripping detection on a mercury-coated glassy carbon electrode, obtaining a detection limit of 0.1 μM of the O-linked glycan $\beta\text{-D-Gal-[1-3]-D-GalNAc}$.

Cui et al.²⁷ have developed a versatile and sensitive immunosensor using CdTe quantum dots as electrochemical and fluorescent labels. This sandwich-type sensor is fabricated on an indium tin oxide chip covered with a well-ordered gold nanoparticle monolayer. The CdTe QDs remaining at the chip surface after the immunological interaction were dissolved and then the amount and identity of the dissolved cadmium ions were determined by square wave stripping voltammetric analysis on a glassy carbon working electrode.

Liu et al.²⁸ have recently described an interesting disposable electrochemical immunosensor diagnosis device that integrates the immunochromatographic strip technique with an electrochemical immunoassay and exploited quantum dots (QD,

CdS@ZnS) as labels for amplifying signal output. The device takes advantage of the speed and low cost of the conventional immunochromatographic strip test and the high sensitivity of the nanoparticle-based electrochemical immunoassays. A sandwich immunoreaction was performed on the immunochromatographic strip, and the captured QD labels in the test zone were determined by highly sensitive stripping voltammetric measurement of the dissolved metallic component (cadmium) with a disposable screen-printed electrode, which is embedded underneath the membrane on the test zone. This device was successfully applied for the detection of prostate specific antigen in human serum sample with a detection limit of 20 pg mL⁻¹.

Voltammetric stripping detection of quantum-dots (CdSe@ZnS) for protein detection has been also reported by Wu et al.²⁹ to detect interleukin-1 alpha (IL-1 alpha) in a sandwich magnetoassay, achieving a detection limit of 0.3 ng mL⁻¹ (18 pM) through the detection of the released cadmium ions. (Fig. 6).

The use of different semiconductor nanoparticles allows the multianalyte detection in a unique assay. A multianalyte electrochemical immunoassay for the simultaneous measurements of proteins (β_2 -microglobulin, IgG, bovine serum albumin, and C-reactive protein) based on the use of different inorganic nanocrystal tracers (ZnS, CdS, PbS, and CuS) was reported by Liu³⁰ et al. In this case, square-wave voltammetric stripping measurements were performed with a glassy carbon disk working electrode to yield fmol detection limits (Fig. 7)

Another multi-analyte electrochemical biosensor, aptamer based, was reported recently by Hansen et al. et al.³¹ using QD tracers for designing with subpicomolar (attomole) detection limits. The multiple biosensing capability is coupled to the enormous amplification feature of nanoparticle based electrochemical stripping measurements to yield remarkably low (attomole) detection limits related to the detection of Cd²⁺ and Pb²⁺ ions released after the QD dissolving using 0.1M HNO₃.

Related to the DNA detection using QDs as labels, a sensitive electrochemical DNA hybridization detection assay, using cadmium sulphide (CdS) nanoclusters as the oligonucleotide labeling tag, was reported by Zhu et al.³². The CdS nanoclusters anchored on the hybrids are dissolved after the hybridization event and the cadmium ions detected by sensitive anodic stripping voltammetry at a mercury-coated glassy carbon electrode, obtaining a detection limit of the target DNA of 2x10⁻¹³ M (Fig. 8).

Wang et al.³³ reported an interesting approach for detection of DNA hybridization using carbon-nanotubes as modifiers of the transducer surface and CdS particle as tracers, obtaining a detection limit of $40 \text{ pg} \times \text{mL}^{-1}$ of DNA target.

Other interesting DNA assay was developed by Sun et al.³⁴ using mercaptoacetic acid (MAA)-modified CdS nanoparticle as label for the detection of nopaline synthase (NOS) terminator gene sequence. The CdS nanoparticles were dissolved and further detected by a sensitive differential pulse anodic stripping analysis, obtaining a detection limit of $2.75 \times 10^{-12} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ of the gene sequence.

On the other hand, Zhu et al.³⁵ used lead sulfide (PbS) nanoparticle tags as labels for the detection of DNA hybridization, measuring the released lead ion concentration by ASV, and detecting 0.3 pmol L^{-1} of the target oligonucleotides.

An example of multi-analyte DNA assay was reported by Wang et al.³⁶ based on the use of different inorganic-colloid nanocrystal tracers (ZnS, CdS and PbS) to differentiate the signals of three DNA targets in connection with a sandwich hybridization assay and stripping voltammetry of the corresponding heavy metals.

Enhancement methods. An enhancement of the analytical signal in the detection of nanoparticles can be achieved by catalytic deposition of other metal on the surface of the nanoparticle, followed by the stripping and detection of this metal. An example of this approach was reported by Mao et al.³⁷. They developed a novel electrochemical protocol for quantification of human IgG based on the precipitation of copper on gold nanoparticle tags and a subsequent ASV detection of the dissolved copper, obtaining a detection limit of 0.5 ng/mL (Fig. 9).

Other catalytic approach was reported by Chu et al.³⁸ based on the precipitation of silver on AuNPs labels using a silver enhancement solution, and chemical reduction of silver ions to silver metal onto the surface of the AuNPs. After silver metal dissolution in an $0.1\text{M HNO}_3/0.6\text{M KNO}_3$ solution, silver ions were determined by anodic stripping voltammetry at a GCE. The method was evaluated for a noncompetitive heterogeneous immunoassay of IgG as a model, achieving a detection limit of $1 \text{ ng} \times \text{mL}^{-1}$, which is competitive with colorimetric enzyme linked immuno-sorbent assay (ELISA). The high performance of the method is attributed to the sensitive ASV determination of silver (I)

at a glassy-carbon electrode (detection limit of 5×10^{-9} M) and to the catalytic precipitation of a large number of silver on the colloidal gold-labelled antibody.

2.2.2. Potentiometric stripping analysis

Potentiometric Stripping Analysis (PSA) is an alternative stripping technique used for the electrochemical detection of nanoparticles after their dissolution. In this technique, just like stripping voltammetry, deposited reaction products or adsorbed substances are stripped from the electrode. The stripping itself can be done either by using a chemical reaction or by using an external current and during the stripping process, the potential is recorded and processed. From the response, recalculated to (dt/dE) vs E , the amount of stripped material can be determined from the peak size and the nature of the species can be deduced from the peak potential.

In this way, Wang *et al.*³⁹, pioneered in 2001 a nanoparticle-based electrochemical detection of DNA hybridization, based on PSA detection of the colloidal gold tag. Signal amplification, and lowering of the detection limits to the nanomolar and picomolar domains, were achieved by precipitation of gold or silver⁴⁰, respectively, onto the colloidal gold label.

The same authors¹⁵ have reported later another PSA approach for measurements of cadmium ions, released from CdS nanoparticles used as labels in a DNA magnetoassay using a thick-film electrode transducer. A nanoparticle-promoted cadmium precipitation is used to enlarge the nanoparticle tag and amplify the stripping DNA hybridization signal achieving a low detection limit (100 fmol) (Fig. 10).

A selective and sensitive gold nanoparticle and PSA based method was reported by Hannae *et al.*⁴¹ for the detection of hepatitis B virus DNA sequences, using magnetic beads as platforms. After separation of non-complementary sequences, hybridized magnetic beads were treated with streptavidin-modified gold followed by silver enhancement, at a gold screen-pinted electrode. High selectivity and high sensitivity were obtained using PSA of silver ions that were deposited on gold nanoparticles, estimating a detection limit of the DNA strand about 0.7 ng mL^{-1} .

Kawde *et al.*⁴² reported other work combining catalytic enhancement and PSA detection for a DNA assay. The assay is based on oligonucleotides functionalized with polymeric beads carrying numerous gold nanoparticle tags. This is combined with a catalytic enlargement of the multiple gold tags and an ultrasensitive chronopotentiometric stripping analysis of the dissolved gold tags, on screen-printed carbon electrodes. Such amplified electrical transduction allows detection of DNA targets down to the 300 amol level (Fig. 11).

2.2.3. Voltammetric measurement of catalytic current

Recent exploited strategies to detect NPs are based on the voltammetric measurement of other chemical reagents based on the catalytic effect of NPs. This strategy presents the advantage that does not require excess reagents simplifying by this way the assay. Furthermore the sensitivity is improved due to the catalytic effect of the NPs.

In this way, Polsky *et al.*⁴³ used nucleic acid-functionalized PtNPs as catalytic labels to amplify the electrochemical detection of both DNA hybridization and aptamer/protein recognition. The assay is based on the catalytic effect of the PtNPs on the reduction of H_2O_2 to H_2O , using gold slides as electrodes. The amperometric measurement of the electrocatalyzed reduction of H_2O_2 allows the detection of DNA with a detection limit of 1×10^{-11} M. In a similar way, the association of aptamer-functionalized PtNPs to a thrombin aptamer/thrombin complex allows the electrocatalytic detection of thrombin up to 1×10^{-9} M.

The same author⁴⁴ has described a novel strategy to create “electrocatalytic antibodies” for further applications in biosensing. Antibodies are previously immobilized onto AuNPs and then, Pd is deposited onto the AuNPs surface, forming core-shell Au/Pd NPs. These NPs exhibit catalytic activity over the oxygen reduction to H_2O , and this effect is approached to indirectly detect the immobilized antibody by measuring the catalytic current of this reduction at glassy carbon electrodes (Fig. 12)

On the other side, Selvaraju *et al.*⁴⁵ have recently developed a nanocatalyst based electrochemical immunoassay, using indium tin oxide electrodes as transducers, magnetic beads as immobilization platform, and AuNPs as electrocatalytic labels for a sandwich immunological assay. The AuNPs produce p-aminophenol from p-nitrophenol by catalytic reduction in the presence of NaBH_4 , and the generated p-

aminophenol is electrooxidized at the electrode. The oxidized product, p-quinone imine, is reduced back to p-aminophenol by NaBH_4 and then re-electrooxidized at the electrode, obtaining a greatly amplified electrochemical signal. In this way, very low detection limits of mouse IgG, of 1 fg/mL (7 aM) using cyclic voltammetry and 100 ag/mL (0.7 aM) using differential pulse voltammetric measurements, were obtained (Fig. 13).

3. Potentiometric techniques

Potentiometric measurements involve the determination of the potential difference between either an indicator or a reference electrode or two reference electrodes separated by a permselective membrane, when there is no significant current flowing between them. Ion-selective electrode (ISE) based on thin films or selective membranes as recognition elements for pH, F^- , I^- , CN^- , Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , NH_4^+ , Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Cu^{2+} etc. or even gases (i.e. CO_2 , NH_3) are the most reported. The potential differences between these indicator and reference electrodes are proportional to the logarithm of the ion activity or gas fugacity (or concentration), as described by the Nernst-Donnan equation. This is only the case when: (i) the membrane or layer selectivity is infinite or if there is a constant or low enough concentration of interfering ions; and (ii) potential differences at various phase boundaries are either negligible or constant, except at the membrane-sample solution boundary.

Recently some emerging novel possibilities of potentiometric immunosensing based on nanoparticle labeling and ion-selective microelectrodes (ISEs) with very low detection limits are announced. These works indicate that ISEs with improved detection limits may be attractive for detection of bioassays.

Recent improvements in the detection limits of ion-selective electrodes based on polymeric membranes containing selective receptors (ionophores) yielded sensors for the direct measurement in the subnanomolar concentration range. This was made possible by minimizing passive zero current ion fluxes from the membrane into the sample solution. It is now possible to use miniaturized ISEs for detecting femtomole

amounts of ions in microvolume samples since there is no expected deterioration of the signal or detection limit as the sample volume is reduced.

Bakker's group pioneered the use of potentiometry for ultrasensitive nanoparticle-based detection of protein interactions⁴⁶. In particular, a silver ion-selective electrode (Ag-ISE) was used as an effective transducer for sandwich immunoassays in connection to the capture and silver enlargement of gold nanoparticle tracers. This approach may form the basis for highly sensitive bioaffinity assays (Fig. 14).

An interesting application of these potentiometric biosensors has been reported by Tang et al.⁴⁷ for the detection of hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg) by self-assembling gold nanoparticles to a thiol-containing sol-gel network. A cleaned gold electrode was first immersed in a hydrolyzed (3-mercaptopropyl) trimethoxysilane sol-gel solution to assemble a three-dimensional silica gel, and then gold nanoparticles were absorbed onto the thiol groups of the sol-gel network. Finally, hepatitis B surface antibody was assembled onto the surface of the gold nanoparticles. The self-assembling procedure was characterized by cyclic voltammetry and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy. Detection is based on the change in potentiometric response, in pH 7.4 buffer solution, before and after the antigen-antibody reaction.. The linear range obtained was from 4 to 960 ng/mL with a detection limit of 1.9 ng/mL and the lifetime was 1 month. Analytical results of several specimens using the developed technique showed satisfactory agreement with those from an ELISA method. This method shows promise for detecting HBsAg in clinical specimens.

More recently, a potentiometric bioaffinity assay for proteins has been reported by Thurer et al.⁴⁸ via CdSe semiconductor nanocrystal traces on a secondary antibody, according to a sandwich immunoassay in microtiter plate format. CdSe quantum dots labels are oxidatively dissolved with hydrogen peroxide and released cations are detected with cadmium ion-selective microelectrode (Fig. 15).

4. Conductometric techniques

Conductance is a measure of the ability of a material to transfer electricity and includes electronic conduction through solids and ionic conduction through liquids. The factors

that affect the magnitude of resistance are exactly the same for conductance, being related by the equation:

$$L = \frac{1}{R}$$

where R is the resistance.

Conductometric biosensing systems are based on the fact that the specific biological interaction occurring on a supporting surface may vary the resistance/conductance of the substrate.

A drawback associated with conductometric biosensors is that it is difficult to overcome problems with non-specificity, as the resistance of a solution is determined by the migration of all ions presents. Therefore, in a complex matrix such as a biological sample, the high ionic strength of the medium may mask the comparatively small net conductivity change caused by the biointeraction. In this context, metal nanoparticles represent an excellent labelling system able to generate significant resistance changes upon the binding event.

A pioneering work where metal nanoparticles were used to amplify resistance changes in relation to a biorecognition event was published by Velev and Kaler in 1999. They used latex microspheres with immuno-active sites on the surface to fill the gaps between the planar electrodes. After the interaction with the target analyte a direct conductivity read out was accomplished after secondary tagging with AuNPs and silver enhancement treatment achieving a limit of detection of 0.2 pM⁴⁹ (Fig. 16).

A similar approach was followed by Mirkin and co-workers in 2002. They developed a conductometric sensor device for DNA analysis immobilizing short “capture” oligonucleotide strands between two fixed microelectrodes (gap 20 μm). The specific binding occurs with the target oligonucleotide in solution which has also recognition elements complementary to oligonucleotide-modified AuNPs. The latter, therefore, after the incubation, fill the electrode gaps varying the conductance. The sensitivity of the device was further increased by means of a catalytic Au-promoted deposition of Ag with hydroquinone reaching a limit of detection of 0.5 pM of target DNA⁵⁰ (Fig. 17).

The use of AuNPs was also exploited by Kim et al., (2000) who developed a disposable immunochromatographic sensor for on-site quantitative determination of human serum

albumin (HSA). The conductometric measurement was carried out in a membrane strip sensor based on two interdigitated silver electrodes screen-printed on a nitrocellulose membrane. 20 nm AuNPs modified with polyaniline (a conducting polymer) were used for the signal generation⁵¹.

The amplification strategies adopted in these works for electrical signal generation involved multiple steps of deposition or enhancement. Hence, there is a trade off between simplicity and sensitivity. More recently a novel DNA conductive sensor was developed by Gao et al. (2007) in which the signal generation is achieved directly by conductive indium tin oxide nanoparticles connected to the probe oligonucleotides by the phosphate groups. The association of these nanoparticles with hybridized nucleic acid molecules led to the formation of an ITO nanoparticle network in the electrode gaps that significantly increased the conductance. The presence of target nucleic acids in the sample solution was therefore detected without amplification steps or Ag enhancement treatments and with limit of detections down to 25 fM⁵² (Fig. 18).

5. Impedance techniques

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) is a very powerful tool for the analysis of interfacial capacitance/resistance changes occurring at conductive or semiconductive surfaces. A perturbing sinusoidal voltage signal is applied to the electrochemical cell, and the resulting current response is measured. Electrochemical transformations occurring at the electrode/electrolyte interface can be modelled by extracting components of the electronic equivalent circuits that correspond to the experimental impedance spectra⁵³.

The impedance spectroscopy represents not only a suitable transduction technique to follow the interfacial interactions of biomolecules, but it also provides a powerful method for the characterization of the structural features of the sensing interfaces⁵⁴.

Metal NPs have been recently adopted in impedimetric-based biosensing applications with the main goal to amplify electrical signals generated by biorecognition events occurring at the electrode surface.

CdS nanoparticles have been adopted by Travas-Sejdic et al. (2006) to amplify the electrochemical signal after the detection of specific oligonucleotide (ODN) fragments. The sensor was based on electropolymerization of a conducting polymer (polypyrrole) in the presence of the probe ODNs. The resulting trapped ODN(s) were then incubated with the complementary target CdS-labeled ODN solution. A significant improvement in sensor sensitivity was observed comparing this system with one where the metal nanoparticles were not used with the detection limit of 0.8 and 13.7 nM, respectively⁵⁵.

A similar strategy was adopted by Fang et al. (2003) that covalently immobilized DNA probes onto a self-assembled mercaptoacetic acid monolayer modified gold electrode; then, after hybridization with the target ssDNA-CdS nanoconjugate, used EIS to detect the change of interfacial electron transfer (R_{et}) of the redox marker $[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-/3-}$, from solution to transducer surface. A remarkably increased R_{et} value was observed only when complementary DNA sequence was used compared with three-base mismatched or non-completely matched sequences under the optimized experimental conditions.

The results showed that CdS nanoparticle labels on target DNA improved the sensitivity of two orders of magnitude when compared with non-CdS tagged DNA sequences⁵⁶.

AuNPs were used recently by Bonanni et al. (2007) in a DNA sensing device for impedimetric signal amplification. They used streptavidin-coated gold nanoparticles to specifically bind the target biotinylated oligomer after the hybridization event. The probe oligomer was adsorbed onto a graphite epoxy composite electrode (GECE) surface and the impedance measurement was performed in a solution containing the redox marker ferrocyanide/ferricyanide. In their work a silver enhancement treatment was performed at the end to visualize the hybridization extension on the electrode surface by SEM, offering moreover a further signal amplification strategy⁵⁷.

This has been in fact used by Moreno-Hagelsieb et al. (2004) to amplify the capacitance signal between interdigitated aluminium electrodes imprinted over an oxidized silicon wafer. This type of electrode surface reduces the non-specific precipitation of silver that occurs on conventional noble metal electrodes. A change in capacitance by a factor of at least two, using DNA solutions down to 0.2 nM, spotted on the electrodes, was observed⁵⁸.

6. Scanning electrochemical microscopy based probes

The scanning electrochemical microscopy (SECM) is an ultra-sensitive detection technique with interest for future bioanalytical applications. It is a scanned probe microscopy (SPM) related to the familiar scanning tunnelling and atomic force microscopes. All SPMs operate by scanning or "rastering" a small probe tip over the surface to be imaged. In SECM, imaging occurs in an electrolyte solution with an electrochemically active tip. In most cases, the SECM tip is an ultramicroelectrode (UME) and the tip signal is a Faradaic current from electrolysis of solution species. Some SECM experiments use an ion-selective electrode (ISE) as a tip. Two features distinguish SECM from related methods such as electrochemical STM or AFM: the chemical sensitivity of the SECM tip and the use of solution phase ions or molecules as the imaging signal. The substrate perturbs the electrochemical response of the tip, and this perturbation provides information about the nature and properties of the substrate.

SECM is a very effective means of probing the conductivity of a substrate and offers a very convenient means of unequivocally determining insulating or metallic behaviour. When the tip, immersed in a solution containing an electroactive mediator, approaches an insulator, the current decreases with tip/substrate distance, d (called negative feedback), while when it approaches a conductor under the same conditions, the current increases (positive feedback).

Very recently SECM has begun to be used as an alternative electrochemical technique to characterize metal and semiconductor nanoparticles which still present unanswered questions regarding for example the relationship between the particle size and the atomic composition/structure with the electrochemical or chemical reactivity.

The reactivity of planar surfaces has been well investigated but there are many new unexplored aspects involved in the reactivity of nanoparticle surfaces. Most reported methods only measure the average properties of the particles present on the surface. One of the first uses of SECM to investigate the properties of metal nanoparticles has been illustrated by Quinn *et al.* (2001). They follow the compression of a monolayer of monodisperse thiol-capped Ag nanoparticles during the transition insulator-metal (I-M) on a Langmuir trough, demonstrating the high sensitivity of SECM in the investigation of nanoparticle-film conductivity changes with the particle interdistances⁵⁹. The linear and also the cross-film conductivity of polyelectrolyte/nanoparticle multilayer were also measured by Ruiz *et al.* (2003) and the sensitivity of SECM allowed the quantification

of the conductivity of a single nanoparticle monolayer. The increase in SECM tip current with the number of polyelectrolyte/nanoparticle layer pairs demonstrated that the layers are not electrically insulated from each other and that there is significant electrical communication between nanoparticles in different layers⁶⁰ (Fig. 19).

The ultimate goal of these studies is to understand the nature of metal nanoparticles that have size-dependent properties, especially the stabilized monolayer protected clusters (MPCs), as well as their potential in applications such as catalysis, nanoscale circuits, machines, and chemical sensors.

In 2004 Georganopoulou et al. used SECM to measure the electron transfer rate between gold monolayer-protected clusters (Au MPCs) (dissolved in organic phase and redox species in aqueous solution⁶¹ (see Fig. 20).

While there have been extensive studies of single molecules, including catalytic properties of single enzymes, usually via fluorescence methods, the behaviour of single MNPs as catalysts remain relatively unexplored. In single molecule studies, the high signal amplification required is provided by the repeated excitation and emission of a suitable stable fluorescent label or product. Amplification in electrocatalysis studies on single MNPs occurs by the repeated electron-transfer reactions that occur at the particle but require the detection of currents in the picoampere or sub-picoampere region. SECM was employed very recently by Tel-Vered and Bard (2006) for the first time to both synthesize and characterize a single metal nanoparticle on a conductive carbon support. Using this approach they avoided the problems arising from multi-nanoparticle synthesis such as narrow size distribution, surface agglomeration, occurrence of lattice defects, and poisoning of the metal by impurities. They synthesized single Pt and Ni nanoparticle and were able to electrochemically characterize them exploiting their catalytic features toward H^+ or O_2 ⁶².

The works illustrated demonstrate the exceptional sensitivity of this technique able to investigate intrinsic electrochemical properties and also catalytic features of single nanoparticles. The ability to detect currents in the order of picoamperes or sub-picoamperes could be exploited in the future for bioanalytical applications reaching limits of detections much lower than conventional techniques.

7. Conclusions

In most of the reported works, nanoparticles are used as labels for the analysis of proteins or DNA sequences, exploiting their direct or indirect electrochemical determination. Gold nanoparticles and quantum dots are the most reported labels used in connection to electrochemical stripping analysis (ESA).

ESA provides simple NP detection methodologies in addition to the cost efficiency of the related instruments. The reported applications of these technologies in DNA sensing and immunosensing have shown significant improvements in terms of sensitivity. Compared to other electrochemical techniques (i.e. conductometric, potentiometric, impedimetric) the possibility for simultaneous detection in the same sample and using the same transducing platform is also another important advantage of ESA.

Potentiometric methods, mostly presented by the use of ion selective electrodes (ISE) are offering novel opportunities for NP related bioanalysis. The low detection limits and miniaturization possibilities achieved so far by ISEs are opening to these interesting application fields such as DNA and protein analysis.

Conductometric and impedimetric technologies are showing advantages in terms of miniaturization and even micro and nanodimensions of the corresponding measuring devices. Nevertheless the application of these technologies is still related to indirect detection of NPs used as labels either by using amplification /enhancement (i.e. silver deposition onto AuNPs) or the use of redox species.

Some recent works based on scanning electrochemical microscopy for the investigation of metal and semiconductor nanoparticles, were presented in the last section of this review with the aim of illustrating the extraordinary sensitivity achievable by this technique, which could be exploited for ultra-sensitive bioanalytical applications.

Although the shown differences, the electrochemical technologies in general are opening the way of new research fields and applications with interest for fields like nanobiotechnology, nanobiomedicine beside others. The integration of the mentioned technologies with scanned probe microscopes will bring, without doubts, significant inputs to the single biomolecule studies related to diagnostic, therapy and controlled drug delivery with interest for human health control.

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http://www.nanocat.org/dataeng/recerca/biopriv/Curriculum_Vitae_Adriano_Ambrosi.pdf)

CAPTION FOR FIGURES

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the electroanalytical protocol for direct voltammetric determination of AuNPs using GECE.

Fig. 2. Magnetic collection and solid-state detection of (A) CdS QDs onto SPE; (B) 1.4nm Au₆₇ QD onto magneto GECE; and (C) AuNPs onto magneto GECE.

Fig. 3. Detection of hybridization using Au Nanoparticle-tagged capture probes. With permission from [21; **Error! Marcador no definido.**].

Fig. 4. Schematic representation of the principal for Au nanoparticle-based detection of protein phosphorylation. The phosphorylation and biotinylation of the immobilized peptide on a screen-printed carbon electrode (SPCE) (1) is followed by the attachment of streptavidin-coated Au nanoparticles (2). The reduction signal of Au nanoparticles was monitored using differential pulse voltammetry (DPV). With permission from [22].

Fig. 5. (A) Schematic representation of the electrochemical stripping detection of DNA hybridization based on silver nanoparticle label. (B) ASV response of 0.1 μM AgNO₃ in 10 mM HNO₃-10 mM KNO₃ solution. With permission from [25].

Fig. 6. Scheme of the QD-based electrochemical assay of IL-1 alpha. (a) Magnetic beads based sandwich immunoassay; (b) cadmium released with 1 M HCl; (c) SWV measurement of the released cadmium ions. With permission from [29].

Fig. 7. Multiprotein detection protocol based on different inorganic nanocrystal tracers. (A) introduction of antibody-modified magnetic beads; (B) binding of the antigens to the antibodies on the magnetic beads; (C) capture of the nanocrystal-labeled secondary antibodies; (D) dissolution of nanocrystals and electrochemical stripping detection. With permission from [30].

Fig. 8. (A) Schematic representation of the electrochemical stripping detection of DNA hybridization based on CdS nanoparticle label. (B) ASV response. With permission from [32].

Fig. 9. Schematic representation of the immunoassay for the detection of human IgG based on copper enhancement. With permission from [37].

Fig. 10. Stripping potentiograms for 0.4 mg L⁻¹ target, without (A) and with (B) catalytic enhancement with 30 μL of 10 mM Cd(NO₃)₂ and 30 μL of 0.05 M hydroquinone. With permission from [15].

Fig. 11. Schematic representation of the amplified analytical protocol. a) hybridization event; b) catalytic enlargement; c) gold dissolution; d) stripping detection. With permission from [42].

Fig. 12. (A) Scheme depicting the preparation of Au/Pd modified antibodies. (a) Mono-NHS 1.4 nm Au-NPs are covalently attached to anti-mouse TNF- α antibody. (b) Pd is deposited onto the Au-NP seeds. (B) Linear sweep voltammetric response upon increasing concentrations of antibody: 0, 0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1, 10 and 100 ppb; a–g respectively. Inset: Current response taken at 2400 mV for increasing concentrations of antibody. With permission from [44].

Fig. 13. (A) (a) Schematic representation of the preparation of a protein modified electrode; (b) schematic view of the preparation of an immunosensing complex; (c) schematic view of the attraction of the immunosensing complex to a modified indium tin oxide electrode (ITO) and the electrochemical detection of mouse IgG. (B) Differential pulse voltammograms of modified indium tin oxide electrodes obtained after a 10-min incubation in a Tris buffer containing 5mM NP and 5mM NaBH₄ at a scan rate of 5 mV/s in the presence of an external magnet. During this measurement, the electrodes were incubated with an immunosensing complex that captured (i) 0, (ii) 100 ag/mL, or (iii) 1 fg/mL mouse IgG. With permission from [45].

Fig. 14. Schematic representation of the potentiometric detection of sandwich immunoassay. (a) antigen addition; (b) capture of the gold nanoparticles labelled anti-mouse IgG antibody; (c) catalytic deposition of silver ions on the conjugated Au nanoparticles; (d) silver dissolution and potentiometric detection using a Ag⁺ selective electrode (ISE). With permission from [46].

Fig. 15. (A) Design of the Cd²⁺ selective micropipete electrode (a) and experimental assembly for potentiometric microtiter plate measurement (b). (B) Schematic of a potentiometric affinity assay for proteins using CdSe as labels. With permission from [48].

Fig. 16. Schematics of the main stages of sensor assembly and functioning. The procedure is illustrated by an immunoglobulin test (Right). SEM micrographs of gold-tagged and silverenhanced latex bridges between electrodes in IgG-specific experiments. (A) Protein A-functionalized latexes heavily coated by deposited metal that short-circuits the electrodes. (B) Nonfunctionalized particles in the negative control

patches only marginally tagged by deposited metal. The bridge remains nonconductive (Left). Adapted from [49].

Fig. 17. Conductivity DNA assay in which gold is accumulated in the gap and later on a silver enhancement procedure in the presence of hydroquinone is performed. With permission from [Error! Marcador no definido].

Fig. 18. Schematic representation of the nucleic acid biosensor based on direct tagging of the hybridized target nucleic acid with ITO nanoparticles and electrical detection. With permission from [52].

Fig. 19. Schematic of the experimental setup. With permission from [60].

Fig. 20. (A) Schematic diagram of SECM approach measurement of the ET rate between an organic-soluble MPC and an aqueous redox species. Electroneutrality is maintained by transfer of perchlorate ions across the interface. (B) Differential pulse (lower) and steady state (upper) voltammetry of 0.4 mM $\text{Au}_{38}(\text{PhC}_2\text{S})_{24}$ clusters in 1,2 dichloroethane solvent obtained at 3-mm-diameter Pt disk at 10 mV/s (lower) and 12.5 μm radius microdisk electrode (upper). The solution contained 0.01 M Hx_4NClO_4 (Hx_4N =tetra-n-hexylammonium). Oxidation states of MPCs corresponding to a given DPV peak or CV wave are identified in the figure. Potentials are corrected vs. standard hydrogen electrode scale. With permission from [61].

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